

Kinetic Characteristics for Reaction between Trichloroisocyanuric (TCCA) Acid with 2-Chlorobenzylidene Malononitrile (CS)

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Abstract— The research experimental results determining rate constant of the reaction between TCCA and CS according to Arrhenius equation was studied. Basing the set of graphs showing the relationship between $(\ln(k) - (1/T))$ and $(\ln(k/T) - (1/T))$, the activation energy (E_a) according to the Arrhenius equation and activation enthalpy variation (ΔH^\ddagger), activation entropy variation (ΔS^\ddagger), free activation energy Gibbs (ΔG^\ddagger) according to the Eyring equation are determined. The products of TCCA reaction and CS at pH = 9 are 2-chloro benzaldehyde oxirane-2,2-dicarbonitrile, 3-(2-chlorophenyl) so predicting the reaction mechanism consists of two reactions taking place in parallel, a hydrolysis and oxidation reactions.

Keywords— Trichloroisocyanuric acid, 2-chlorobenzylidene malononitrile, Kinetic characteristics.

I. INTRODUCTION

2-chlorobenzylidene malononitrile (CS) is heavily used in the Vietnam War, statistics show that about 9,000 tons of CS were used on the battlefield [1]. Due to being durable, difficult to decompose, it can be found that CS existed since the war in Central and Southern Vietnam. That the reason we need to deal with the amount of residual CS found. Reactions that are often used to dissolve CS [4], [8] include:

CS hydrolysis reaction takes place as follows:

and CS oxidation reaction by OCl^- takes place as follows:

Acid trichloroisocyanuric (TCCA) is hydrolyzed to form hypochlorous acid HOCl and acid cyanuric as following [3]

However, not all chlorine content in TCCA hydrolyzed into HOCl. Thus a part of chlorine still exists in TCCA called bound available chlorine [6]. TCCA is hydrolyzed to produce HOCl and depending on pH and then HOCl proceeding hydrolyze to form OCl^- [7].

So, the solution TCCA has a pH > 7 that can react with CS in two reactions (1) and (2). From the Arrhenius equation, E_a - activation energy (kJ/mol) was determined [6]; From the Eyring equation determine ΔH^\ddagger - Activated enthalpy variation (kJ/mol), ΔS^\ddagger - Activated entropic variation (kJ/mol.K) and calculate ΔG^\ddagger - Free energy variability Activated Gibbs (kJ/mol) [6]. Use GC/MS method to determine the product of TCCA reaction and CS from which to predict the mechanism of reaction.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Apparatus and Chemicals

2.1.1 Apparatus

UV-Vis Spectrophotometer UV-VI Jasco V530, Japan

Gas chromatography/Mass spectrometry GC 6895 / MS HP 5975A, USA

2.1.2 Chemicals

TCCA (Sigma - Aldrich);

Solid CS with 99.0% purity (Vietnam);

Other used chemicals for research and analysis include: Na_2SO_4 , phosphate buffer pH = 9, NaOH, KCl, H_2SO_4 , FeCl_2 , sodium 1,2-naphthoquinone-4-sulfonate, ethanol, (Pa, Sigma- Aldrich) , acetonitrile, methanol, dichloromethane, chloroform, n-hexane (Pa, Merck).

2.2 Experimental procedure

2.2.1 Prepare the solution

Mix 50 mg of CS in 100 ml of ethanol to obtain CS solution with a concentration of 495.00 mg / L (2.652 mM / L) to obtain solution S1.

Mixing 960 mg of TCCA in 500ml of distilled water obtained TCCA solution with a concentration of 1,920.00 mg / L (8.261 mM / L) obtained S2 solution.

Take in the reaction flask 5ml of phosphate buffer pH = 9, 10mL of solution S1, 10mL of solution S2 to obtain solution S3 have: $C_{\text{CS}} = 198.00 \text{ mg / L}$; $C_{\text{TCCA}} = 768.01 \text{ mg / L}$.

2.2.2 Determine the parameters of the reaction

2.2.2.1 Determine the reaction level

After 3-minute; 5 minutes; 10 minutes; 15 minutes; 25 minutes, take sample S3 solution, analyze the remaining CS concentration. Develop a graph showing the relationship ($\ln(C_{\text{CS}}) = f(t)$). If the graph is linear, then the reaction is an apparent pseudo first order reaction.

2.2.2.2 Determine the reaction rate constant

Determine the reaction rate constant. If the reaction between TCCA and CS determined according to 2.2.2.1 is level 1, the reaction rate is expressed by the equation:

$$v = \frac{-dC}{dt} = k_A(C_o - x) \quad (4)$$

In which: k_A is the reaction rate constant according to Arrhenius (s^{-1})

C_o is the concentration of CS at time $t = 0 \text{ s}$ (mol/L)

x is the concentration of CS participated in the reaction

$$(C_o - x) = C_{\text{CS}}$$

In which: C_{CS} is the concentration of CS at time t in solution (mol/L)

Transformation (4) is obtained:

$$\ln(C_{\text{CS}}) = -k_A t + CT \quad (5)$$

In which: CT is an integral constant

t is the reaction time (s)

The equation has the form of $y = ax + b$ with $y = \ln(C_{\text{CS}})$; $a = -k_A$; $x = t$; $b = CT$.

The reaction rate constant is determined as follows:

$$k_A = -a \quad (6)$$

2.2.2.3. Determination of E_a according to the Arrhenius equation

Arrhenius equation is as follows:

$$k_A = Ae^{\frac{-E_a}{RT}} \quad (7)$$

Inside:

k_A is the reaction rate constant according to Arrhenius (s^{-1})

T is the absolute temperature (K)

A is the exponential factor. According to collision theory, A depends on the frequency of collisions in the right direction and is considered to be independent of T.

E_a is activation energy (kJ/mol)

R is the ideal gas constant ($R = 8,315 \text{ J/mol.K}$)

The transformation of equation (7) is obtained:

$$\ln k_A = \frac{-E_a}{RT} + \ln A \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) has the form of $y = ax + b$ with $y = \ln(k_A)$; $a = -E_a/R$; $x = 1/T$; $b = \ln A$.

Maintain the temperature of S3 solution at the temperature respectively: 293 K, 298 K, 303 K, 313 K. Determine the reaction rate constant at the temperatures according to 2.2.2.2.

Develop a graph showing the relationship ($\ln(k_{A-CS}) = f(1/T)$). Then, activation energy is calculated according to the formula:

$$E_a = -a.R \text{ (J/mol)} \quad (9)$$

2.2.2.3. Determination of ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger according to the Eyring equation:

Eyring equation:

$$k_A = \frac{k_B T}{h} e^{\frac{-\Delta H^\ddagger}{RT}} e^{\frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{R}} \quad (10)$$

Equation transformation (10):

$$\ln \frac{k_A}{T} = -\frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{R} \frac{1}{T} + \ln \frac{k_B}{h} + \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{R} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) has the form of $y = -ax + b$, where $x = 1/T$; $y = \ln(k_A/T)$; and $a = \frac{-\Delta H^\ddagger}{R}$, $b = \ln \frac{k_B}{h} + \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{R}$

From that set of graphs shows the relationship between ($\ln(k) - (1/T)$) (11):

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = -a.R \text{ (J/mol)} \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = R(b - \ln(k_B/h)) \text{ (J/mol.K)} \quad (13)$$

Free activation energy Gibbs (ΔG^\ddagger) follows the equation:

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger - T\Delta S^\ddagger \text{ (J/mol)} \quad (14)$$

2.2.3. Methods of analysis

2.2.3.1. Analysis of CS by UV-Vis Spectrophotometry

Sampling S3 solution in experiments, analyzing CS concentration on the Jasco-V530 UV / VIS device based on the reaction between CS and 1.2 naphthoquinon-4-sunfonatium reagent in alkaline medium, CS concentration in The solution is determined by measuring the optical absorbance of the solution and comparing it with the calibration graph. Analytical

samples were dissolved in solvents; dehydration in the analytical sample by Na_2SO_4 ; Filter about 5 μl as a sample by Whatman filter [2].

2.2.3.2. Analysis of reaction products by GC/MS

Sampling solution S3 when $t = 25$ minutes, $T = 298$ K, product analysis of the reaction between TCCA and CS on HP 5975A device. Sample run program [5]: Using 03 column types with different degree of polarization are: SPB1 column size (30m*0.32mm*0.25 μm); DB5-MS column size (30m*0.32mm*0.25 μm), column OV1701 size (30m*0.32mm*0.25 μm). Temperature at the beginning of column 60 $^\circ\text{C}$, hold for 1 minute, increase 8 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 280 $^\circ\text{C}$, keep at that temperature for 10 minutes. Air flow rate carries (He) is 1mL/min. Scan range of 45-800M/z. Universal library NIST 2005 with about 195.000 substances.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Level of reaction between TCCA and CS

The graph shows the relationship ($\ln(C_{\text{CS}})$ -t) of CS reaction with TCCA at 298 K shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. Graph of relationship representation ($\ln(C_{\text{CS}})$ -t) of CS response with TCCA

From Figure 1, the reaction between TCCA and CS has C_{CS} concentration decreased linearly over time (t), so the reaction between CS and TCCA is pseudo first order reaction with a correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.9832$.

3.2 Kinetic study of TCCA reaction with CS

Rate constant of reaction between TCCA and CS at different temperatures in Table 1.

TABLE 1
THE REACTION RATE CONSTANT BETWEEN TCCA AND CS AND CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Number order	Kind	k (s^{-1})	R^2
1	TCCA-CS-293	0.0014	0.9680
2	TCCA-CS-298	0.0031	0.9832
3	TCCA-CS-308	0.0043	0.8845
4	TCCA-CS-318	0.0069	0.9306

From Table 1, the reaction rate constant in TCCA-CS systems increases with increasing temperature, consistent with the Arrhenius equation. The correlation coefficients of the graph represent each middle relationship ($\ln(C_{\text{CS}})$ -t) at different temperatures ranging from 88.45% (TCCA-CS-308) to 98.32% (TCCA-CS-293).

FIGURE 3. GC chromatography of (a) CS solution at pH = 9 and (b) reaction product of TCCA-CS

According to the chromatogram of the reaction product of TCCA-CS system (Figure 3. a) and the NIST spectrum of MS-library 2005, there was no pic with the time of retention in the reaction solution. It was $t_R = 14.367$ minutes for 2-Chlorobenzalmalononitrile (CS). This proves that there is no CS in the post-reaction solution.

On the chromatogram of the reaction product solution (Figure 3. b), there appears pic with retention time of $t_R^1 = 8.154$ minutes corresponding to 2-chloro benzaldehyde and pic has a retention time of $t_R^2 = 12.2$ minutes corresponding to oxirane-2, 2-dicarbonitrile, 3- (2-chlorophenyl).

From the theory of CS poisoning and the results of product analysis of the toxic reaction CS by TCCA, can be predicted at pH = 9 TCCA with hydrolysis and the poisoning process consists of two reactions that occur in parallel and create products as follows:

TCCA hydrolysis reaction:

Hydrolysis reaction:

Redox reaction:

IV. CONCLUSION

From the results of the study it can draw the following conclusions:

- The reaction between TCCA and CS is consistent with collision theory and activated complex theory.
- The reaction between TCCA and CS at 298 K is a pseudo- first-order reaction with $k_A = 0.0031$ (s^{-1}), $E_a = 57.65$ (kJ/mol); $\Delta H_{298}^\# = 55.13$ (kJ/mol); $\Delta S_{298}^\# = -0.11$ (kJ/mol.K); $\Delta G_{298}^\# = 87.78$ (kJ/mol).
- The reaction between TCCA and CS includes two parallel reactions that are hydrolysis reaction and oxidation reaction, producing two main products such as 2-chloro benzaldehyde and oxirane-2,2-dicarbonitrile, 3- (2-chlorophenyl).

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